

COMPREHENSIVE ENERGY CONSUMPTION ANALYSIS OF CONVENTIONAL VEHICLES BASED ON DESIGN PARAMETERS

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Abstract: The fuel consumption of conventional vehicles is significantly influenced by their design parameters. During the traction phase, the engine-generated power is utilized to overcome resisting forces, mainly including aerodynamic drag and tyre rolling resistance. The remaining mechanical power accelerates the vehicle according to the driver's desired speed profile. In contrast, during the braking phase, the vehicle's mechanical energy is converted into heat on the frictional surfaces of conventional brakes, resulting in substantial losses and reduced overall efficiency. This research employs a quantitative approach to dissect the energy distribution of conventional vehicles during their operation. The total energy consumption of each contributing factor is individually evaluated under standard driving cycles. To simplify the analysis, a flat road profile is assumed, neglecting the impact of weight variations on uphill and downhill slopes. Utilizing a validated backward vehicle model, the longitudinal dynamics of the two commercially available conventional vehicles were simulated. These insights into vehicle energy distribution provide parameter optimization for improved performance and efficiency.

Keywords: *Vehicle energy consumption factors, engine fuel consumption, vehicle dynamics, aerodynamic and rolling resistance.*

Аннотация: На расход топлива обычных транспортных средств существенное влияние оказывают их конструктивные параметры. На этапе тяги мощность двигателя используется для преодоления сил сопротивления, в основном включая аэродинамическое сопротивление и сопротивление качению шин. Оставшаяся механическая мощность ускоряет автомобиль в соответствии с желаемым профилем скорости водителя. Напротив, во время фазы торможения механическая энергия автомобиля преобразуется в тепло на фрикционных поверхностях обычных тормозов, что приводит к значительным потерям и снижению общей эффективности. В этом исследовании используется количественный подход для анализа распределения энергии обычных транспортных средств во время их эксплуатации. Эти данные о распределении энергии транспортных средств позволяют оптимизировать параметры для повышения производительности и эффективности.

Ключевые слова: *Факторы энергопотребления автомобиля, расход топлива двигателя, динамика автомобиля, аэродинамическое сопротивление и сопротивление качению.*

Introduction

Reducing carbon dioxide emissions from passenger vehicles is a major concern in the automotive industry. To address this, manufacturers are optimizing mechanical components and design parameters. Additionally, the electrification of conventional vehicles is another strategy to lower emissions.

According to vehicle longitudinal dynamics, during automobile motion, the power generated by the power source is used to counteract resistive forces such as aerodynamic drag, tire rolling resistance, and other transmission

losses. The remaining power propels the vehicle at the desired speed and acceleration. The main resistive forces: aerodynamics and rolling friction.

When a vehicle is moving, the density and viscosity of the air create a force that opposes its movement. These forces are primarily dependent on the shape of the vehicle and result from pressure differences between the front (higher pressure) and rear (lower pressure) sides of the vehicle, resulting in a force that acts in the opposite direction to the movement of the vehicle. C_d - The coefficient of drag is a function of the vehicle frontal area (A_{front}), vehicle speed (v) and air density (ρ) [1].

$$F_a = \frac{1}{2} \rho \cdot C_d \cdot A_{front} \cdot v^2$$

The weight (P) of the car causes the tyres to deform so that the contact with the ground becomes an area rather than a point. When the car is stationary, the contact pressure is uniform. However, when the car is moving, the contact pressure profile becomes asymmetrical. As a result, when the tyre rolls, this contact force induces a resistive torque. The rolling resistance of tires depends on tire characteristics and its kinematic model can be expressed as:

$$F_{rolling} = P \cdot f_r$$

Where rolling coefficient can be found as [2]:

$$f_r = 0.01 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{v}{160}\right)$$

While inertia forces depend on mass of the vehicle. The total required traction force is:

$$F_{tr} = M \cdot \frac{dv}{dt} + F_a + F_r + F_{gr}$$

where, F_{gr} - vehicle weight force components along the motion. For simplicity, this force considered as zero. Which means simulation is carried out along the flat road.

This paper analyzes and compare energy consumption fac of two GM conventional automobiles Tracker 2 and Onix which are equipped with the same engine. The main specifications which will be used to model vehicle dynamics are reported in the following figure.

	Tracker 2	Chevrolet Onix
Engine displacement	1199 cm ³	1199 cm ³
Engine power	130 Hp @ 5500 rpm.	132 Hp @ 5500 rpm.
Curb weight	1200 kg	1117 kg
Length x width x Height	4270 x 1791 x 1627 mm	4474 x 1730 x 1474 mm
Tires size	215/60 R16	185/70 R14

Figure 1: Specifications of Tracker2 and Onix conventional vehicles. [3] [4]

Then the backward simulation model has been developed as represented in figure 2. Detailed description of each block can be found in our previous work [5]. The specifications of Tracker 2 and Onix was used for the model and it is simulated for UDDS driving cycle.

Figure 2: Backward simulation model of conventional vehicle.

Simulation results for Tracker 2

The simulation results for Tracker 2 automobile including its velocity profile, corresponding traction total force on tire, aerodynamic, rolling, inertia and in braking forces was plotted in figure 3.

Figure 3: Simulation results for Tracker 2 automobile.

The corresponding power for each force can be evaluated as:

$$P = F \cdot v$$

Then integrating the power by time along the whole driving cycle, energy consumption for each force can be obtained:

$$E = \int P dt$$

Energy consumption of each factor was evaluated and summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Energy consumption factor of Tracker 2 for UDDS driving cycle.

As shown in the pie chart, 37% of the engine's generated power is used to accelerate the vehicle, 23% is dissipated during braking, 22% is used to overcome rolling resistance, and the remaining power is consumed by aerodynamic forces.

Simulation results for Onix

The conventional vehicle's backward model has been updated with the specifications of the Onix automobile and simulated for the UDDS driving cycle. The results are summarized in Table 2. For a clearer view, these results are also presented in a bar chart (see Figure 4).

Table 2: Energy consumption of Onix under UDDS cycle

Factors	Energy consumption
Energy for overcoming aerodynamics	1.089 MJ
Energy used for rolling resistance	1.427 MJ
Energy for accelerating the vehicle	2.437 MJ
Braking energy	-1.517 MJ

To compare the performance of the two vehicles, the simulation results are plotted together in one frame, as shown in Figure 5. From the figure, it can be seen that the aerodynamic force is slightly lower for the Onix automobile,

as it has a smaller frontal area. The rolling resistance force is also slightly lower due to the Onix having smaller tires, resulting in a smaller tire radius and therefore a shorter lever arm for the rolling resistance force.

Figure 4: Energy consumption of Onix conventional vehicle
 Figure 5: Comparison of simulation results for Onix and Tracker 2.

Conclusion

The paper investigates the energy distribution in a vehicle, considering various factors such as overcoming resistive forces, braking losses, and energy consumption during acceleration. To conduct this analysis, two vehicles—Onix and Tracker 2, both falling within the same conventional class—were utilized and their results were compared. The findings are summarized in Table 3.

Here are the key observations:

- Onix exhibits 12.5% less energy consumption when overcoming aerodynamic resistance.
- Due to its smaller tire size, Onix consumes 7% less energy for rolling resistance.
- With a smaller mass, Onix requires 9% less energy for acceleration.
- Additionally, Onix experiences 6.4% less braking energy compared to Tracker 2.

These insights highlight the energy efficiency advantages of the Onix model

Energy consumption by	Tracker 2	Onix
Aerodynamic resistance	1.244 MJ	1.089 MJ (-12,5 %)
Rolling resistance	1.533 MJ	1.427 MJ (-7 %)
Accelerate vehicle	2.618 MJ	2.437 MJ (-9 %)
Total traction	5.395 MJ	4.953 MJ (-9 %)
Braking energy	-1.62 MJ	-1.517 MJ (-6.4%)

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